
Farmers' Perception of Problems of Sugarcane Cultivation: A Pilot Study of Selected Villages of Kolhapur division

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Abstract:

Sugarcane Farming is one of the important segments of Indian Agriculture because it is raw material to sugar industry for which India ranks second in the world economy. Indian sugar industry provides employment opportunity to nearly 50 million growers (Mangala & Shrinivasa, 2012:21) Hence, sugarcane farming has significant role in the agro economy as a whole. The present study covers the farmers' perception regarding fertilizer, irrigation, seed, disease and soil problem of sugarcane farming with reference to Kolhapur division: Kolhapur, Sangli, Satara. The farmers' perception towards fertilizer, irrigation, seed, disease and soil problem was needed to be studied. This paper has made an attempt to study the farmers' perception towards some aspects like Soil erosion due to inadequate fertilizer management, availability of training to farmers for quality seed production, availability of scientific disease management system. The present study explores the different functional aspects of the sugarcane farming that will help to understand their different problems. This study is also helpful to sugar factories and Government authorities to make appropriate policies and it will help to uplift the life of poor farmers. This study is also helpful to develop knowledge based system so that IT based farming help to improve cultivation practices.

Introduction:

Sugarcane is known from the earliest times and is referred to in historical records going back in the remote days in ancient civilization, which flourished long before the Christian era. However, the actual extraction of sugar has been discovered with later. Sugarcane Farming is one of the important segments of Indian Agriculture because it is raw material to sugar industry where India ranks second in the world economy. Indian sugar industry provides employment opportunity to nearly 50 million growers (Mangala & Shrinivasa, 2012:21). Hence, sugarcane farming has significant role in the agro economy as a whole. The present study covers the farmers' perception regarding fertilizer, irrigation, seed, disease and soil problem of sugarcane farming with reference to Kolhapur division: Kolhapur,

Sangli, Satara. But farmers' perception towards the problem in cultivation of sugarcane was needed to be studied.

Literature Review:

Expert Systems for Sugarcane:

Aravinda Reddy and M. S. Prasad Babu, in their paper entitled “Semantic Web Based Sugarcane Expert System using Support Vector Machines” presents a Semantic web based expert system for sugarcane crop. The paper explains detail architecture of expert system which has two main modules namely informative system and Expert systems. Informative systems are designed by constructing ontologies by using Web Ontology Language. Jena framework is used to retrieve the data from OWL. SWRL rules are used to build Inference engine. This rule-based expert

system can be used to diagnose various diseases and pests, encountered in sugarcane crop by using support vector machine algorithm. (Babu, 2006)

F. Silva, S. Massruhá, R. Deus, A. Santos, V. Barbieri, S. Cruz and E. Malavolta, in their paper entitled "A web-based expert system for diagnosis of nutritional" presents a web-based expert system for diagnosis of plant nutrient disorders in sugarcane. The system can be useful to provide information for identification of essential and functional plant nutrient disorders in sugarcane to avoid deficiency and to solve nutritional problems arising from the development of this culture. The knowledge base created using expert knowledge of sugarcane farmer, research scientist, extension specialist, student, and consultant. The first version of system was developed using the virtual diagnosis framework developed by Embrapa and CENA/USP. The paper also discussed adopted development methodology and the current status of the system for diagnosis of nutritional deficiency in sugarcane. (F. Silva S. M., 2011.)

Knowledge based applications of artificial intelligence have enhanced productivity in varied fields of science and technology. Sugarcane, a long duration crop is ravaged by many insect and non-insect pests limiting the cane yield. T. Rajula Shanthy and N. Mukunthan in their paper "SUGAR-EX: An information and communication technology based decision making tool" focuses on an expert system for diagnosis of sugarcane pests and their management. This expert system takes into consideration sixteen major pests of sugarcane utilizing their symptoms/details of pest stages as identification cues. The primary goal of this expert system is to make expertise on sugarcane pests and their management available to sugarcane development personnel and cane growers in

a portable computer based kiosk. (Mukunthan, 2009.)

S S Hasan and R K Isaac in their paper entitled "An integrated approach of MAS Common KADS, Model-View-Controller and web application optimization strategies for web-based expert system development" presents a framework for development of web based expert system with integrated approach of MAS Common KADS agent oriented methodology, Model View Controller (MVC) architecture and Web application optimization strategies in order to achieve high usability. Study was also work out the plan of various modules, their content type and content structure for high usability and efficiency. The paper also guides in software engineering of developing such system with respect to Internet Technologies. Application of this framework for developing web-based expert system in sugarcane disorder diagnosis has been developed using proposed framework and demonstrated along with evaluation results. (Isaac, 2011)

Statement of Problem:

Now days, Sugarcane is the main source of sugar in India and holds a prominent position as a cash crop. Sugarcane is a renewable, natural agricultural resource because it provides sugar, besides biofuel, fiber, fertilizer and myriad of byproducts/co-products with ecological sustainability. Because of fluctuated rate of other crop, farmers have to increase yield of sugarcane to maintain profit ratio. (B*, 2019) To increase yield, farmer should have complete knowledge of different Sugarcane crop management factors or they need expert who help or advise them to take decisions related to different crop management factors. Means if farmer got complete knowledge or an Expert then definitely they will get high yield which turns into high profit. To address these problems, there should be Knowledge Based

System which will help or guide farmers into management of different crop management factors and so Researcher intended to carry out the research entitled. Few questions raised into the mind of researcher like, What are the major problems facing by farmers regarding seed management, soil management, water management, fertilizer management and disease management.

Objectives of the Research:

1. The proposed study is undertaken with specific objective as under
2. To study problems faced by farmers while taking decision related to different Sugarcane crop management factors.

Hypothesis:

H0-There is no significant difference between Seed Selection, Soil Preparation, Water Management and Fertilizer Management and disease management problem faced by farmers in different districts.

H1: There is significant difference between Seed Selection, Soil Preparation, Water Management and Fertilizer Management and disease management problem faced by farmers in different districts.

Pilot Study:

Researcher carried out an initial pilot survey for pre-testing the questionnaires. The purpose of the pilot study was to test the quality of items in the questionnaires and to confirm the feasibility of the questionnaires. In the present study Cronbach's alpha test was applied to find the reliability of questionnaires.

A. About Cronbach's Alpha:

Reliability refers to the assessment of the degree of internal consistency between multiple measurements of a variable. The reliability can be increased by

providing questions which are clear about what respondents are being asked. The questionnaire should be designed such that the respondents are familiar with the questions and the questions themselves are relevant to the respondents. The most commonly used measure of reliability is internal consistency. The most accepted measure of a measure's internal consistency is the Cronbach's alpha. A value of 0.60 was used as the practical bound to demonstrate internal consistency.

B. Questionnaire:

The sugarcane irrigation, fertilizer, seed, disease, soil problems were studied with well-structured questionnaire. A comprehensive questionnaire was prepared in Marathi to collect data from farmers keeping in view the main objective and hypothesis of study. Questionnaire for the The details of the questionnaire are enclosed in Annexure 1 in English. The questionnaire incorporated different scaling techniques as demanded by the study.

C. Sample Data:

In the study farmers are at the centre place. They are respondents who provide information regarding their understanding, opinion, experiences and perception towards sugarcane irrigation problems. 70 farmers were selected for pilot study. The details are shown in Table No 1

Table No 1: Sample Size

Respondents	Farmers
Kolhapur	25
Sangli	15
Satara	10

D. Reliability Statistics Table No 2 shows case processing summary. Reliability of questionnaires was tested and found to be satisfactory by using Cronbach's alpha test as shown.

Table No 2: Reliability Statistics

Farmers	
Valid Cases	Cronbach's Alpha
70	.812

Source: Pilot data compiled by researcher through SPSS

Table No 3: Demographic Profile of Sugarcane Growers

Demographic variables	Classifications	No. of Respondent	Percentage (%)
District	Kolhapur	25	35.71
	Sangli	25	35.71
	Satara	20	28.57
Age group	20-30	8	11.42
	31-40	16	22.85
	41-50	21	30
	51-60	19	27.14
	61>	6	8.5
Qualification	Below SSC	1	1.42
	SSC	20	28.57
	HSC	19	27.14
	Diploma	10	14.28
	Graduation	17	24.28
	PG	3	4.28

Table no 3 shows demographic profile of sugarcane growers selected for the study.

It can be observed that out of total sample data 25 (35.71 %) farmers have been selected from Kolhapur, 25(35.71%) from Sangli and 20 (28.57 %) from Satara district. 30 % sugarcane growers belong to the 41-50 age group and 27.14 % sugarcane growers belong to the age group of 51-60. 70% farmers are above SSC.

Sugarcane growers are well matured by age as most of the farmers are between 41-60 years of age and are literate so that they can use any expert system if developed.

Hypothesis Testing:

Hypothesis 1

Ho: There is no significant difference between irrigation problems faced by farmers in different districts.

H1: There is a significant difference between irrigation problems faced by the farmers in different districts

To test this hypothesis, 70 farmers were selected from 3 districts of Kolhapur division. Opinion of the respondents were recorded on a likert scale, where 1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree. The data is tabulated in SPSS. Table No. 3 shows the analyzed data of farmers.

Table No. 4 Descriptive Statistics and District Wise Ranks of Respondents for Irrigation management problems

Ranks					
Irrigation management problems	District	N	Mean Rank	Mean	Std. Deviation
1. Cannot get exact water requirement for sugarcane	Kolhapur	25	38.58	4.00	1.007
	Sangli	25	32.36		
	Satara	20	35.58		
	Total	70			

2. Cannot get sufficient water for irrigation	Kolhapur	25	33.06	1.89	.671
	Sangli	25	38.70		
	Satara	20	34.55		
	Total	70			
3. Cannot get water as and when required because of common irrigation schemes	Kolhapur	25	33.86	2.43	.791
	Sangli	25	38.70		
	Satara	20	33.55		
	Total	70			
4. Cannot implement new automation tools because of common irrigation schemes	Kolhapur	25	36.58	4.20	.861
	Sangli	25	34.02		
	Satara	20	36.00		
	Total	70			
5. No proper irrigation management	Kolhapur	25	38.20	4.19	.728
	Sangli	25	32.52		
	Satara	20	35.85		
	Total	70			
6. Cannot get electricity regularly for irrigation	Kolhapur	25	34.52	3.47	.793
	Sangli	25	33.22		
	Satara	20	39.58		
	Total	70			

Source: Data compiled by researcher using SPSS

Table No. 5 Test Statistics ^{a,b}						
	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6
Chi-Square	1.326	1.258	1.149	.251	1.262	1.381
df	2	2	2	2	2	2
Asymp. Sig.	.515	.533	.563	.882	.532	.501

Source: Data compiled by researcher using SPSS

From table no 5 it is observed that the statistical significance level of the Kruskal Wallis test i.e., the p-value of all problem statements considered are more than 0.05 and, therefore, Ho accepted i.e There is no significant difference between irrigation problems faced by farmers in different

districts, i.e. Kolhapur, Sangli and Satara districts.

Hypothesis 2

Ho: There is no significant difference between fertilizer problems faced by farmers in different districts.

H2: There is a significant difference between fertilizer problems faced by the farmers in different districts.

Table No. 6 Descriptive Statistics and District Wise Ranks of Respondents for Fertilizer management problem

Ranks					
Fertilizer management problems	V1	N	Mean Rank	Mean	Std. Deviation
1.No scientific fertilizer management system	Kolhapur	25	36.00	3.90	1.024
	Sangli	25	36.24		
	Satara	20	33.95		
	Total	70			

2. Cannot get exact fertilizer requirement for sugarcane	Kolhapur	25	36.46	3.91	1.004
	Sangli	25	32.26		
	Satara	20	38.35		
	Total	70			
3. Cannot get sufficient fertilizer for cultivation	Kolhapur	25	38.16	3.44	0.879
	Sangli	25	29.04		
	Satara	20	40.25		
	Total	70			
4. Soil erosion due to inadequate fertilizer management	Kolhapur	25	34.98	3.89	1.057
	Sangli	25	37.44		
	Satara	20	33.73		
	Total	70			
5. Sugarcane yield decrease due to chemical fertilizer	Kolhapur	25	37.70	4.19	1.011
	Sangli	25	38.88		
	Satara	20	28.53		
	Total	70			

Source: Data compiled by researcher using SPSS

Table No. 7 Test Statistics^{a,b}

	B1	B2	B3	B4	B5
Chi-Square	.185	1.221	4.677	.446	3.951
df	2	2	2	2	2
Asymp. Sig.	.911	.543	.096	.800	.139

Source: Data compiled by researcher using SPSS

From table no 7 it is observed that the statistical significance level of the Kruskal Wallis test i.e., the p-value of all problem statements considered are more than 0.05 and, therefore, Ho accepted i.e There is no significant difference between fertilizer problems faced by farmers in different districts, i.e. Kolhapur, Sangli and Satara districts.

Hypothesis 3

Ho: There is no significant difference between seed problems faced by farmers in different districts.

H2: There is a significant difference between seed problems faced by the farmers in different districts

Table No. 8 Descriptive Statistics and District Wise Ranks of Respondents for seed management problems

Ranks	V1	N	Mean Rank	Mean	Std. Deviation
1. Lack of high quality seeds	Kolhapur	25	39.26	3.81	1.067
	Sangli	25	30.72		
	Satara	20	36.78		
	Total	70			
2. Lack of availability of quality seeds to the growers by Sugar factories.	Kolhapur	25	37.34	3.57	.672
	Sangli	25	37.34		
	Satara	20	30.90		
	Total	70			

3.Lack of availability of training to farmers for quality seed production	Kolhapur	25	28.48	3.81	1.107
	Sangli	25	39.18		
	Satara	20	39.68		
	Total	70			
4.Use of sugarcane seed from own farm.	Kolhapur	25	32.30	4.10	.950
	Sangli	25	40.48		
	Satara	20	33.28		
	Total	70			
5.Lack of Scientific seed management deteriorates seed production strategies and methods.	Kolhapur	25	29.80	4.27	.883
	Sangli	25	35.08		
	Satara	20	43.15		
	Total	70			

Source: Data compiled by researcher using SPSS

Table No. 9 Test Statistics^{a,b}

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
Chi-Square	2.656	1.764	5.283	2.792	5.825
df	2	2	2	2	2
Asymp. Sig.	.265	.414	.071	.248	.054

Source: Data compiled by researcher using SPSS

From table no 9 it is observed that the statistical significance level of the Kruskal Wallis test i.e., the p-value of all problem statements considered are more than 0.05 and, therefore, Ho accepted i.e. There is no significant difference between seed problems faced by farmers in different districts, i.e. Kolhapur, Sangli and Satara districts.

Hypothesis 4

Ho: There is no significant difference between disease problems faced by farmers in different districts.

H2: There is a significant difference between disease problems faced by the farmers in different districts.

Table No. 10 Descriptive Statistics and District Wise Ranks of Respondents for disease management problems

Ranks					
Disease management problems	V1	N	Mean Rank	Mean	Std. Deviation
1.Cannot get early warning of disease	Kolhapur	25	34.80	4.04	1.148
	Sangli	25	38.28		
	Satara	20	32.90		
	Total	70			
2.Cannot get exact Pesticides requirement for sugarcane	Kolhapur	25	36.84	3.89	1.234
	Sangli	25	24.50		
	Satara	20	47.58		
	Total	70			
3.Cannot get sufficient Pesticides for cultivation	Kolhapur	25	33.98	2.47	.737
	Sangli	25	38.52		
	Satara	20	33.63		

	Total	70			
4. Cannot use non-chemical /biological pest control	Kolhapur	25	28.60	4.50	.676
	Sangli	25	35.76		
	Satara	20	43.80		
	Total	70			
5.No scientific disease management system available	Kolhapur	25	33.80	4.46	.863
	Sangli	25	34.36		
	Satara	20	39.05		
	Total	70			

Source: Data compiled by researcher using SPSS

Table No. 11 Test Statistics^{a,b}

	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5
Chi-Square	.944	16.099	1.100	8.205	1.178
df	2	2	2	2	2
Asymp. Sig.	.624	.000	.577	.017	.555

Source: Data compiled by researcher using SPSS

From table no 11 it is observed that the statistical significance level of the Kruskal Wallis test i.e., the p-value of all problem statements considered are more than 0.05 and, therefore, H_0 accepted i.e. There is no significant difference between disease problems faced by farmers in

different districts, i.e. Kolhapur, Sangli and Satara districts.

Hypothesis 5

Ho: There is no significant difference between soil problems faced by farmers in different districts.

H2: There is a significant difference between soil problems faced by the farmers in different districts.

Table No. 12 Descriptive Statistics and District Wise Ranks of Respondents for soil management problems

Ranks					
Soil management problems	V1	N	Mean Rank	Mean	Std. Deviation
1.Addition of nonorganic matter is practiced.	Kolhapur	25	33.28	4.16	1.016
	Sangli	25	35.20		
	Satara	20	38.65		
	Total	70			
2.erratic and imbalanced use of chemical fertilizer	Kolhapur	25	39.48	4.41	.807
	Sangli	25	29.36		
	Satara	20	38.20		
	Total	70			
3.poor yield of sugarcane due to non-organic farming	Kolhapur	25	31.44	3.99	1.083
	Sangli	25	33.48		
	Satara	20	43.10		
	Total	70			
4.Soil fertility gets deteriorating due to exceed the quantities of nutrients	Kolhapur	25	28.36	4.21	.976
	Sangli	25	33.84		
	Satara	20	46.50		
	Total	70			

Source: Data compiled by researcher using SPSS

Table No. 13 Test Statistics^{a,b}

	E1	E2	E3	E4
Chi-Square	.918	4.586	4.601	10.852
df	2	2	2	2
Asymp. Sig.	.632	.101	.100	.004

Source: Data compiled by researcher using SPSS

From table no 13 it is observed that the statistical significance level of the Kruskal Wallis test i.e., the p-value of all problem statements considered are more than 0.05 and, therefore, H_0 accepted i.e. There is no significant difference between

soil problems faced by farmers in different districts, i.e. Kolhapur, Sangli and Satara districts.

Like to implement expert system for sugarcane Crop for Fertilizer, irrigation, soil, seed and disease management in your farm

Graph No:1 Like to implement Expert System

From above graph it is observed that sugarcane growers from Kolhapur, sangli, satara districts are more inclined trend to implement expert system for Fertilizer, irrigation, soil, seed and disease management. Around 91.42 percent farmers said they will like to implement system which shows combined results for vital parameters of sugarcane in one application and should be user friendly and mobile based.

Conclusion:

Expert system pre-implementation study was carried out to identify irrigation,

fertilizer, seed, disease, soil problems of sugarcane faced by the farmers in Kolhapur division. These problems were considered as base for development of expert system. It was observed that irrigation, fertilizer, seed, disease, soil problems faced by farmers are similar in nature from one district to another district. It is concluded that practices adopted by different farmers from different district are in same nature result in facing similar structure of problems. Also utmost farmers are interested to implement expert system which give real time solution for different parameters in one application.

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